

Effect of solvents on regioselectivity of anisole nitration

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Abstract : Nitration of anisole dissolved in different solvents with 70% (w/v) nitric acid was studied. Solvents were observed to strongly influence positional selectivity and rate of nitration. The *ortho/para* ratio remained virtually constant (~1.2) in nonpolar solvents, but varied considerably with polar solvents. It appeared to have a linear correlation with the ratio of solubility of water in solvent to dielectric constant. Conversion also seemed to be linearly correlated with inverse of solubility of water. Reactions were found to occur in both organic and aqueous phases. In general, better conversions and yields were obtained in nonpolar solvents. The order of preference is : *n*-heptane > cyclohexane > *n*-hexane > carbon tetrachloride. The process is also environment friendly.

Keywords : Anisole, nitration, solvent, regioselectivity.

Introduction

Nitration of anisole has long been of research interest and has received much attention due to varieties of nitrating agents, variation of isomers, yield of reaction, formation of phenolic by-products, kinetics and mechanism of the reaction¹⁻¹⁶. The earliest quantitative studies on nitration of anisole¹ reported the yield of nitroanisoles to be only 30% when mixed acid or nitric acid were used as nitrating agents which are very common industrial nitrating agents. Later, Bunton *et al.*² studied extensively the nitration of anisole, *p*-chloroanisole and phenol using nitric acid in acetic acid, and reported that a part of anisole got oxidized under the nitrating condition and produced nitrous acid which in turn led to autocatalysis. Intense purple coloured by-product, diaminyloxidoammonium nitrate was found to form during nitration. They also proposed a mechanism for demethylation of anisole, which led to phenolic nitro-products. Thus it appears that in strong nitrating media, low yield of nitroanisoles may therefore be due to demethylation of anisole and formation of coloured by-products.

Later studies on the mechanism of electrophilic aromatic nitration¹⁷⁻²⁸ showed that a second reaction path was possible and active, and this allowed formation of

phenolic nitro-products and also explained low conversion to the nitrated product. Polar two-electron (Ingold-Hughes²⁷), Scheme 1 and Single Electron Transfer (SET, Kenner and Weiss²⁸), Scheme 2 appeared to present two limiting reaction pathways. Esteves *et al.*²⁵ reported that the importance of these two mechanisms would depend on the solvent, experimental conditions and oxidation potential of the substrate. Queiroz *et al.*²⁶ suggested that in both the mechanisms the extent of reaction depends on the ability of aromatic compounds to transfer an electron to NO₂⁺. Therefore ring substituents have strong effects on the mechanism of the reaction. It was also reported that benzene (the parent aromatic compound) is in the border line of the process, i.e. it may follow classical Ingold-Hughes mechanism or single electron transfer (SET) mechanism depending on reaction condition, whereas ring deactivating substituents bearing aromatics follow Ingold-Hughes mechanism and activating substituents bearing aromatics follow single electron transfer mechanism. They also explained the role of polar protic and aprotic solvents on nitration reaction. Apart from the mechanism of aromatic nitration reaction, variation of product isomer, i.e. regioselectivity of substituted aromatic is also a topic of research. From the mechanistic point of view, π -com-

Scheme 1. Polar mechanism.

Scheme 2. Single electron transfer mechanism [Kenner^{28a}; Weiss^{28b}].

plex (Scheme 2) is not the product determining step^{17,24}. The positional selectivity is determined by the atomic spin population of aromatic cation radical, $\text{ArH}^{\bullet+}$ ^{21,24,25} and it is being established in the collapse of the SET intimate pair into the σ -complex. Ring substituents should have therefore strong effect on positional selectivity of the substrate and it is internal factor of the aromatic. But external factors such as temperature, pressure and medium of nitration reaction have also an interesting role on positional selectivity of aromatic as revealed from several investigations^{19-21,23,29-35}.

The *ortho/para* ratios varied enormously for nitration of anisole with different solvents and Paul³⁰ suggested that it is largely influenced by dipole between the aromatic ring and substituent, electrophilic species, i.e. nitronium ion and dielectric constant of the medium. Others^{26,32} reported that polarity of the medium is responsible. Liljenberg *et al.*³⁴ calculated the relative stabilities of the σ -complex intermediates using density functional theory. They found that the method is useful for prediction of regioisomer for halogenation of aromatics and nitration of heterocyclic substrates but failed to predict regioselectivity for nitration of monosubstituted benzenes. They concluded that elaborate model systems including solvent molecules are necessary for quantitative prediction of *ortho/para* isomer. Germain³⁵ reported that a single property of the solvent could not explain the positional selectivity of anisole. Another aspect of nitration of anisole is to develop a milder reaction condition, which would reduce use of strong acid and also be cleaner, cheaper, environment friendly and simpler. In this connection, many

workers used/developed solid catalysts like perfluorinated resinsulfonic acid (Nafion-H)⁴, zeolite beta-I¹⁵, silica sulphuric acid¹⁶. Nitration of anisole using Nafion-H catalyst requires *n*-butyl nitrate which is costly and cannot be used in industrial scale. The preparation of silica sulphuric acid is hazardous, as it needs chlorosulphonic acid which is very corrosive and fumeous, and the reaction also evolves hydrochloric acid gas. Yield of nitroanisoles is only 49% with zeolite beta-I and its recovery from the reaction mixture is also difficult.

Objectives of our investigation are to study the effect of solvent on nitration of anisole and also to develop a process which would be environment friendly with good yield of nitroproducts.

Results and discussion

Two categories of solvents were used to study the effect of solvents on nitration of anisole – polar and non-polar. Reactions were stopped after 30 min by adding ethanol in most cases and in some cases solvent in which reaction was carried out. Experimental results along with some physical properties of the solvents used have been presented in Table 1. The conversions of anisole at 30 min using different solvents against inverse of the solubility of water in the organic solvent have been depicted in Fig. 1 corresponding to the data presented in Table 1. It is of interest to note that, with the exception of data obtained using carbon tetrachloride, the rest show a very good linear correlation. Reaction also occurs in acetonitrile and tetrahydrofuran, which being miscible with water form only the organic “solvent rich” phase. It can

Table 1. Nitration of anisole with nitric acid (15.52 M) using various solvents at 25 ± 0.2 °C (30 min)

Solvent	Polarity (Db)	Sol. of water in solvent, mg/100 g of solvent	Dielectric constant	Conversion (%)	Yield (%)		<i>o/p</i> ratio
					Nitroanisole	Nitrophenol	
CH ₃ CN	3.44	Miscible	37.5	4.01	0.07	0.14	0.26
THF	1.75	Miscible	7.58	3.40	0.25	0.16	0.46
C ₆ H ₅ Cl	1.6	40	5.62	12.16	8.17	0	1.41
CH ₂ Cl ₂	1.14	200	8.9	0.85	13.78	1.07	2.04
CHCl ₃	1.01	70	4.8	7.83	1.00	0	1.84
<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₄	0	14	1.88	52.52	40.70	0.03	1.23
<i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₁₆	0	14	1.9	53.94	73.38	0.03	1.19
Cyclo-C ₆ H ₁₂	0	15.5	2	48.10	64.11	0.04	1.20
CCl ₄	0	9	2.2	20.25	57.98	0.06	1.19

Fig. 1. Conversion of anisole vs inverse of solubility of water in different solvents at 25 ± 0.2 °C at 30 min.

therefore be said that reaction occurs in both organic and aqueous phases. Most probably the reaction is faster in aqueous phase compared to that in organic phase, and as the solubility of water increases, the volume of aqueous phase gets reduced and so the rate of reaction. It has also been verified that there was no anisole left after 36 h, irrespective of the solvent used although yields of nitroproducts are different. The *ortho/para* ratio of nitroanisoles in different solvents also exhibits linear relationship with the ratio of water solubility in organic phase to dielectric constant of the solvent. This has been shown in Fig. 2. It has been established that nitration by nitronium ion gives high *ortho/para* ratio whereas low values are the results of nitrosation¹¹, which is a special reaction path for nitration of anisole in presence of 'nitrous acid'. If variation of isomer ratio is only due to the varying amount of fortuitous nitration catalyzed by nitrous acid which is formed during the reaction or present in catalytic amount, then properties of solvent primarily responsible for the generation of varying amount of NO⁺

Fig. 2. *Ortho/para* ratio of nitroanisoles in different solvents vs ratio of solubility of water in solvent to dielectric constant.

ion should be dielectric constant and solubility of water in solvent. Otherwise solvent medium should have strong effect on the product determining step, i.e. the formation of σ -complex.

Results shown in Table 1 also indicate that polar and nonpolar solvents have clear cut distinct effect on regioselectivity of nitration of anisole. Nonpolar solvents maintain a constant *ortho/para* ratio (~ 1.2) whereas polar solvents behave differently. Results are somewhat different from that obtained from the experiments of Germain³⁵. This may be due to the reaction mechanism being followed or the different attacking species, NO⁺ as it depends on reaction condition. Results are consistent with the observations that yields and regioselectivities depend on the nature of the solvent as reported by Cornelis *et al.*³⁶. It is also clear from the results that nonpolar solvents are favourable for nitration of anisole with nitric acid compared to that using polar solvents. This low con-

version/yield in polar media may be due to the fact that the attacking nitronium ion is more strongly solvated in polar media; it is less accessible for coupling with the radical cation of anisole²⁶. This effect has been explained by Szabo *et al.*²⁰ as desolvation barrier. To study the rate of reaction in nonpolar solvents, reactions were continued to 2 h and then stopped by adding appropriate solvent. In all cases, conversions of anisole were found to increase as revealed from the data presented in Table 2. Conversion of anisole was found to be higher with the solvent of lower dielectric constant. Proportions of nitrophenol were also found to increase and formation of phenolic nitro-products may be due to the occurrence of oxygen transfer from neutral NO₂ because of SET mechanism as explained by Queiroz *et al.*²⁶.

Table 2. Nitration of anisole with nitric acid (15.52 M) using various solvents at 25 ± 0.2 °C (2 h)

Solvent	Conversion (%)	Yield (%)	Nitrophenol (%)	<i>o/p</i> ratio
<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₄	72.09	53.04	0.19	1.26
<i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₁₆	72.09	72.76	0.42	1.28
Cyclo-C ₆ H ₁₂	66.36	67.05	0.75	1.25
CCl ₄	38.60	57.06	0.75	1.19

Among the studied nonpolar solvents, the order of preference is : *n*-heptane > cyclohexane > *n*-hexane > carbon tetrachloride for nitration of anisole with nitric acid.

Conclusion

The foregoing discussion revealed the following :

(i) Nitration of anisole occurs in both phases – aqueous and organic. This phenomenon has been explained in our earlier communication (Jana *et al.*³⁷).

(ii) The rate of reaction in aqueous phase is faster compared to that in organic phase.

(iii) Solvent has strong effect on positional selectivity and rate of reaction of anisole with nitric acid.

(iv) If the positional selectivity of nitration of anisole was only determined by the atomic spin population of aromatic cation radical, ArH^{+•}_{21,24,25,38} and it would be independent of influence of solvent matrix²⁰, *ortho/para* ratio should have remained unaltered in different solvents, which is contrary to our experimental observa-

tion. However, it is still not possible to identify the exact process by which the solvents affect the ratio and whether it acts through modification of the nitrosation rate.

(v) It can not be said firmly which mechanism is predominant in a particular solvent. But it is obvious that both the mechanisms are operative as nitrophenols are obtained in all studied solvents except chlorobenzene and chloroform.

(vi) Nonpolar solvents with low dielectric constants are preferable for nitration of anisole with good yield.

Experimental

HPLC grade solvent (3 ml) and 20 μL (1.814 × 10⁻⁴ g mol) anisole were taken in a conical flask fitted with stopper and stirred with a magnetic stirrer at 2000 ± 100 rpm at 25 °C. Then 100 μL (15.52 M, 1.552 × 10⁻³ g mol) of nitric acid was added to the stirring solution. Reactions were stopped after 30 min or 2 h as required by adding HPLC grade ethanol. Sometimes in addition to the ethanol, solvent in which reaction was carried out was added to make the reaction mixture homogeneous. Samples have been analyzed in HPLC (Waters, C8 column). All experiments were carried out at least three times. Commercially available nitric acid 70% (w/v) and anisole (AR grade E. Merck) were used in the investigation. Nitric acid was standardized against standard caustic solution and its strength was 15.52 M (molarity). Anisole was distilled in packed column for purification. Purity of anisole was > 99.4% (assay). All reference compounds were of HPLC grade, procured from Aldrich.

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